

Science

INADEQUATE TREATMENT OF MILK TEETH MISTAKEN FOR PERMANENT TEETH

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Abstract

Introduction of two very worrying cases which just by chance were to my disposal – treatment of milk tooth as a permanent one.

Keywords: Inadequate; Treatment; Milk Teeth.

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1. Introduction

My wish is to introduce two very worrying cases which just by chance were to my disposal. One of the X-rays I kept for long time in my computer and I gave it to colleagues in the University to present it to students. But soon, again just by chance, I came across to a second case very similar to the first one. In my opinion now I should pay attention to all colleagues in private dental clinics to this problem.

Case 1

Before 4 years during a student exercise of Conservative dentistry in Faculty of Dental medicine, MU-Sofia, where I was an Assistant professor, a patient a young woman after her treatment ask the student to make a check-up of her son who was with her and with pain. As an assistant I did accepted with the arrangement to direct the boy of the age of 9 years to student exercises of pediatric dental treatment or to postgraduate student doctors in the department of Pediatric dental treatment. Her story was that now he was with pain after long treatment of permanent tooth with the diagnose “Gangrena”, a post was put into the root canal and a control X-ray was taken. The next step was a crown of the tooth. The treatment was done in a private clinic in “Lulin”, Sofia at the price of 450 lv. As a great surprise of me I saw a milk tooth with post and composite filling. Immediately I asked for an X-Ray. I was shocked to find that the treatment with post was done to a milk tooth (figure 1. The boy with his mother were directed to the surgery department were the brilliant professionals extracted the milk tooth. After two weeks the permanent tooth was on the right place with a little almost invisible enamel scratch from the post but without serious damage to the permanent tooth.

Figure 1: Build –up with a post and composite material to a milk tooth.

Case 2

On 12.09.18 in my private dental office a mother asked me for a consultation for her son who is 12 years old. The mother explained that 08.2017 (a year before) while they were on a vacation in Varna the boy was with a sharp tooth pain. Up to their view the parents found a well-looking and expensive clinic in Varna where a young doctor started a treatment and angry at the parents put the blame on them for the bad condition of their son' permanent tooth with diagnose "Gangrena". The doctor took an X-Ray and started extirpating the pulp, medical treatment, filling the root canal and a filling of composite material. All these were done for 7 days with anesthetic for every meeting, with pain and a lot of bleeding. The little boy was stressed but he did his best and was a good patient. The price was 350lv. A week before I met the patient the 12 years old boy told his mother that a big part of the filling material was lost and that was the reason for the consultation with me. I asked for and X-ray and after that extracted the milk tooth (figure 2). The patient was directed to a specialist to trace the coming –up of the permanent tooth because of the delay due to the false and inadequate treatment.

Figure 2: Initial X-Ray and a photo of the extracted milk tooth

In conclusion I want to remind that anatomy of milk and permanent teeth is studied in the first years of student hood in every Faculty of Dental medicine. When we are not sure, do not hesitate to take an X-Ray. The modern devices are not dangerous with radiation but it is a sin to treat milk teeth as permanent teeth and could lead to real harm. Ignorance of anatomy is a risk, medical error and there is a great possibility to harm the permanent tooth.

Do not feel ashamed to ask for a consultation or help of colleagues!

Dear colleagues, we all make mistakes and that is normal as being human beings. But please be responsible for your actions and examine well the X-Rays – they will give you a lot of information. Our debt is not to harm and also to preserve the dignity of the profession, to study conscientiously and to respect our professors!